

L-Asparaginase: A Promising Enzyme for Treatment of Acute Lymphoblastic Leukemia

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Abstract:

Asparaginases are known to be the cornerstone for treatment of acute lymphoblastic leukemia (ALL) and are used for treatment in all pediatric regimens as well as in the majority of adult treatment protocols. Clinical hypersensitivity reactions against commercially available asparaginase have resulted in failure of asparaginase in treatment of ALL in more than 60% of cases. Thus, it is required to search for serologically different asparaginase from new organisms for the patients exhibiting sensitivity to one formulation of asparaginase, so that they can be switched to another to ensure that they receive the most efficacious treatment regimen possible. The present study report *E. coli* VRY-15, *E. coli* VRY-8 and *E. coli* VRY-14 as potent producer of L-asparaginase. The L-asparaginase obtained from *E. coli* VRY-15 showed highest specific activity i.e., 19.56 $\mu\text{mol}/\text{mg}$. Attempt was made to purify the enzyme. Molecular weight of purified L-asparaginase obtained from *E. coli* VRY-15 was found to be 56 K Da as determined using Sodium dodecyl sulfate polyacrylamide gel electrophoresis (SDS- PAGE).

Key Words: L-asparagine; asparaginase; *E. coli*; acute lymphoblastic leukemia.

Introduction:

Cancer is defined as uncontrolled division of cells. Acute lymphoblastic leukemia is cancer of WBC, characterized by the excessive multiplication of malignant and immature WBC (lymphoblast) in bone marrow. Treatment of acute leukemia includes chemotherapy, steroids, radiation therapy, intensive combined treatments including bone marrow or stem cell transplants. Among these, chemotherapy is most preferred. The drugs being employed for treatment includes prednisolone, dexamethasone, vincristine, asparaginase, daunorubicin, cyclophosphamide, cytarabine, etoposide, thioguanine, mercaptopurine, hydrocortisone, methotrexate etc. Although, variety of drugs are available today, but their efficacy in treatment of cancers at third and fourth stage is doubtful. Also, the side effects caused by these chemotherapeutic agents are many such as infertility, secondary neoplasm, nausea and vomiting, immunosuppression etc.

L-asparaginase (EC 3.5.1.1), a medically important enzyme, hydrolyze L-asparagine (essential amino acid) to aspartic acid and ammonia. Since several types of tumour cells require L-asparagine for protein synthesis, they are deprived of an essential growth

factor in the presence of L-asparaginase, thus, resulting in cytotoxicity of leukaemic cells.

L-asparaginase is a relatively wide spread enzyme, found in many microorganisms such as *Aerobacter*, *Bacillus*, *Pseudomonas*, *Serratia*, *Xanthomonas*, *Photobacterium* (Peterson & Ciegler, 1969), *Streptomyces* (Dejong, 1972), *Proteus* (Tosa et al, 1971), *Vibrio* (Kafkewitz & Goodman, 1974) and *Aspergillus* (Sarquis et al, 2004). The fact that not all L-asparaginase possess antitumour properties seems to be related to the affinity of the enzyme for the substrate and factors affecting the clearance rate from the system (Cornea et al, 2002). Recently, it has been shown that L-asparaginases derived from *E. coli* and *Erwinia carotovora* possess antitumor activity particularly against acute lymphoblastic leukemia (Mashburn & Wriston, 1964). But, administration of such enzyme protein for a long duration, in general, produces the corresponding antibody in the tissues, resulting in anaphylactic shock and may also cause neutralization of drug effect. Therefore, search for new serologically different L-asparaginase with a similar therapeutic effect is highly desirable. The present study, is aimed to isolate new potential organisms possessing L-asparaginase production capacity.

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Materials & Methods:

Sample collection: Sewage water samples were collected in the sterilized sampling bottles for isolation

of *E. coli* from different locations of People's Campus, Bhanpur, Bhopal (M.P).

Isolation of bacterial cultures: In order to isolate the *E. coli* from sewage samples, serial dilution method was used (Waksman & Reilly, 1945). Dilution (10^{-3}) was streaked on the surface of sterilized eosin methylene blue agar (EMB) plates and incubated at 37°C for 24 hours. The colonies possessing green metallic sheen (characteristic of *E. coli* on EMB medium) were isolated, purified and preserved on Sabouraud's dextrose agar (SDA) slants.

Identification of isolated bacterial cultures: Identification of isolated bacterial cultures was done on the basis of its growth characteristics on different differential media and biochemical properties such as Gram's reaction, motility testing, lactose fermentation, indole production, methyl red, Voges proskauer (VP) reaction, citrate utilization, H₂S production, catalase and urease tests using a standard protocol (Holt, 1994).

Determination of asparaginase activity:

(a) Qualitative assay for production of L-asparaginase by isolated *E. coli* cultures: Agar diffusion technique was used for qualitative assay of L-asparaginase by isolated bacterial cultures. Modified Czapek Dox's Medium (pH 6.8) supplemented with sodium nitrate 2.0gm, potassium chloride 0.5gm, magnesium glycerophosphate 0.5gm, ferrous sulphate 0.01gm, potassium sulphate 0.35gm, sucrose 30.0gm, agar agar 12.0gm, L-asparagine (1% w/v), distilled water 1000 ml and phenol red (0.009 % w/v) was used as an assay medium. Sterilized medium (10 ml) was distributed in the presterilized culture tubes to prepare stabs. After that a loopful culture of each isolate was inoculated on the surface of solidified stabs and incubated at 37°C for 24 to 48 hours. Uninoculated stab was regarded as a negative control. Stabs were examined for change in colour of medium from yellowish to pink due to change of pH indicating the positive asparaginase activity. Gradation of asparaginase activity was done on the basis of the extent of colour change of medium. Every experiment was conducted in triplicate.

(b) Production of L-asparaginase: The secondary screening of bacterial isolates for L-asparaginase production was done on modified M9 broth medium

(pH 7) supplemented with L-asparagine (1% w/v), which was inoculated with *E. coli* cultures and incubated for 24 hours at 37°C; 35 ml of medium was taken in a conical flask of 150 ml and inoculated with 1 ml culture of bacteria having density 2×10^6 cell / ml and incubated at 37°C for 24 hours. After completion of the incubation period, culture broth was centrifuged at 5,000 rpm for 20 min at 4°C. To assay intracellular L- asparaginase enzyme's activity, cell pellet was suspended in 15 ml of 0.1M Tris-HCl buffer (pH 7.4) and sonicated using ultra-sonicator for 15 min at 4°C. Cell debris was removed by centrifuging at 4°C for 10 min at 10,000 rpm.

Agar well diffusion technique:

The 100µl of cell free culture broth was poured into the agar well of diameter 8mm prepared in plates containing modified Czapek Dox's Medium. The filtrate was allowed to diffuse into the medium for 12 hours at 4°C. The diameter of zone (mm) of L-asparaginase activity, as indicated by the formation of pink coloured zone around the well against the yellow background, was measured. For further studies, cultures showing greater enzyme production were selected.

Quantitative assay for production of L-asparaginase by isolated bacterial cultures:

The quantitative estimation of enzyme activity was done with selected culture i.e. *E. coli* isolates VRY-8, VRY-14 & VRY-15. Asparaginase activity was measured by method of Mashburn & Wriston (1963). The rate of hydrolysis of L-asparagine was determined by measuring the release of ammonia using Nessler's reaction. The reaction mixture contained 0.5 ml of enzyme sample, 0.5 ml of 0.05 M Tris-HCl buffer (pH 8.6) and 0.5 ml of 0.04 M L-asparagine. The reaction mixture was incubated at 37°C for 30 min. The enzyme activity was stopped by the addition of trichloroacetic acid (TCA 10% w/v). The mixture was then centrifuged at 10,000 rpm for 5 min, and 0.1 ml of the supernatant was taken and to it 3.7 ml of distilled water was added; 0.2 ml of Nessler's reagent (Himedia) was added to the reaction tube and kept at 20°C for 20 min. The absorbance was measured at 450 nm using spectrophotometer. The amount of ammonia liberated was calculated using ammonium standard curve. One unit of L-asparaginase activity is defined as release of one micromole of ammonia per hour at 37°C and pH 8.6.

Determination of protein concentration of crude enzyme samples:

Protein concentration was determined using Bovine serum albumin (BSA) as standard by using Bradford reagent. Different concentrations of BSA were prepared. The volume was made up to 3 ml using distilled water; 1 ml of Bradford reagent was added to each test tube and mixed well. After 30 min of incubation, the absorbance was measured at 595 nm by spectrophotometer and the protein content determined. The crude enzyme samples were processed in a similar manner as described above.

Purification of L-asparaginase:

Purification of intracellular L-asparaginase of *E. coli* VRY-15 was done using gel permeation column chromatography using Sephadex G-100 and its purity was checked using SDS PAGE. Sodium dodecyl sulfate polyacrylamide gel electrophoresis was carried out in using slab gel of 7% acrylamide in a Tris-HCl buffer pH 8.3 containing 0.1% SDS. The gels were stained with 0.025 Coomassie brilliant blue R-250 and de-stained (Stegemann, 1979).

Results:

A total of 35 bacterial strains were isolated from 14 different sewage samples (Table I). All the isolated bacterial cultures were found to be Gram-negative. Their shape varied from bacillus to coccobacillus. They all were found to be motile and possessed green metallic sheen when inoculated on EMB agar plates. Lactose fermentation along with production of acid and gas was observed with all the isolates. They

Table I: Isolation of bacterial cultures from sewage water samples

S.No	Place / Sample source	Isolates
1	Nurses hostel B / block 1 (24)	VRY-1, VRY-2
2	Nurses hostel B / block 2 (20)	VRY-3
3	Nurses hostel A / block 1(19)	VRY-4, VRY-5
4	Dirty drain of hostel (tank-1)	VRY-6, VRY-7, VRY-8, VRY-9
5	Nurses hostel A / block 2 (21)	VRY-10, VRY-11, VRY-12
6	Nurses hostel A / block 3 (15)	VRY-13, VRY-14
7	Nurses hostel A / block 4 (2)	VRY-15, VRY-16, VRY-17
8	Dirty drain of hostel (tank-2)	VRY-18, VRY-19, VRY-20
9	Nurses hostel B / block 3 (13)	VRY-21, VRY-22
10	Nurses hostel B / block 4 (3)	VRY-23, VRY-24, VRY-25
11	Nurses hostel B / block 5 (16)	VRY-26, VRY-27, VRY-28
12	Nurses hostel A / block 5 (17)	VRY-29, VRY-30
13	Nurses hostel A / block 6 (22)	VRY-31, VRY-32, VRY-33
14	Nurses hostel A / block 7 (14)	VRY-34, VRY-35

showed a positive response to indole test and methyl red test and negative response to VP and citrate utilization test. Results of morphological and biochemical studies showed that the isolates belong to the genus *Escherichia*.

Asparaginase activity varied upto great extent among different isolates. Maximum activity of intracellular L-asparaginase was recorded in *E. coli* VRY-15 showing 2.0 cm zone of enzyme activity (Fig. Ia & Ib)

Fig. Ia: Agar diffusion test for L-asparaginase activity in *E. coli* VRY-15.

Fig. Ib: L-Asparaginase activity in culture filtrate of *E. coli* VRY-15

followed by VRY-8 and VRY-14 (Table II). It is obvious from the table that five of the isolates showed moderate activity of this enzyme after 24 h of incubation

Table II: L-asparaginase activity in isolated bacterial cultures

<i>E. coli</i> Isolates	In Solid Medium		L-Asparaginase Activity	
	After 24h.	After 48h.	Extracellular* Enzyme (diameter in cm)	Intracellular* Enzyme (diameter in cm)
	VRY-1	W+	+	-
VRY-2	W+	+	-	0.3
VRY-3	+	+	-	0.3
VRY-4	+	+	-	0.5
VRY-5	+	+	-	0.4
VRY-6	+++	+++	-	1.3
VRY-7	+++	+++	-	1.2
VRY-8	++++	++++	0.3	1.9
VRY-9	W+	+	-	1.3
VRY-10	+++	+++	-	1.3
VRY-11	++	+++	-	1.2
VRY-12	+++	+++	0.2	1.1
VRY-13	W+	+	-	1.0
VRY-14	++++	++++	0.4	1.9
VRY-15	+++++	+++++	0.8	2.0
VRY-16	W+	+	0.2	0.5
VRY-17	-	-	-	-
VRY-18	-	-	-	-
VRY-19	+	++	-	0.2
VRY-20	-	-	-	-
VRY-21	W+	+	0.2	0.4
VRY-22	-	-	-	-
VRY-23	+++	+++	-	0.3
VRY-24	-	-	-	-
VRY-25	+	++	-	0.3
VRY-26	-	-	-	-
VRY-27	-	W+	0.2	0.3
VRY-28	-	+	-	0.2
VRY-29	-	+	0.1	0.4
VRY-30	-	-	-	-
VRY-31	+	+++	0.1	1.4
VRY-32	+	+++	-	1.3
VRY-33	-	-	-	-
VRY-34	-	+	0.2	0.2
VRY-35	-	+	-	0.3

* Excluding the well diameter of 8 mm, + + + + +: Very strong activity, + + + +: Strong activity, + + +: Moderate activity, + + or +: less activity, W +: Weak Positive.

while 6 of them were weak positive and 8 isolates showed no asparaginase production even after 48 h of incubation.

The isolates were grown in broth medium in order to check intracellular and extracellular L-asparaginase producing abilities. Out of 35 isolates, only 10 isolates showed extracellular production of enzyme while 25 isolates did not show the extracellular production of the enzyme. Since most of L-asparaginase reported till date are intracellular, thus all isolates were also checked for intracellular L-asparaginase activity. Twenty seven *E. coli* isolates showed the presence of intracellular L-asparaginase (Table II).

The maximum intracellular activity of L-asparaginase was found in the isolate VRY-15 (2.0 cm) followed by VRY-8 (1.9 cm) and VRY-14 (1.9 cm). Ten of the isolates also showed activity in the range of 1.0 to 1.4 cm. Maximum L-asparaginase activity was found in the intracellular extract of VRY-15 showing 19.56 µmol/mg of specific activity (Table III). Molecular weight of purified L-asparaginase obtained from *E. coli* VRY-15 was found to be 56 KDalton as determined by using SDS- PAGE. Molecular weight of the enzyme was different from that of commercially available L-asparaginase having a molecular weight of 31.73 KDalton.

Discussion:

Asparagine is an originator of acrylamide and is formed during the browning that occurs in frying, baking and grilling of products made from cereal or potato at temperatures exceeding 120°C (www.who.int/ipcs/publications/jecfa/reports/en/index.html). This substance may be carcinogenic and detrimental to human genes as it can cause cancer to many individuals. Discovery of L-asparaginase (L-asparaginase aminohydrolase, EC 3.5.1.1), as a medicinal agent for treatment of cancer, was made in 1922. Asparaginases are enzymes that occur naturally

Table No. III: L- Asparaginase activity in selected *E. coli* isolates

<i>E. coli</i> s train	Intracellular enzyme			Extracellular enzyme		
	Asparaginase Activity (µmol/ml)	Protein Content (mg/ml)	Specific Activity (µmol/mg)	Asparaginase Activity (µmol/ml)	Protein Content (mg/ml)	Specific Activity (µmol/mg)
VRY – 8	0.15	0.856	9.0	1.2	1.963	0.611
VRY – 14	0.21	1.246	10.11	2.4	1.856	1.293
VRY- 15	0.12	0.386	19.56	5.4	1.390	3.88

and are distributed among living organisms including animals, plants and microbes (Mukherjee et al, 2000; Siechiechowicz & Ireland, 1989; Clementi, 1922) The importance of micro-organisms as L-asparaginase sources has been focused since the time it was obtained from *E. coli* and its anti-neoplastic activity demonstrated in guinea pig serum (Schawartz et al, 1966; Boyse et al, 1967). The *E. coli* and *Erwinia* enzymes were isolated, purified and experimentally used as an anti-leukaemic agent in human patients (Story et al, 1993). It demonstrated high potential against acute lymphoblastic leukaemia (Oettgen et al, 1967). Several research groups have studied asparaginase production and purification in an attempt to minimize impurities that produce allergenic reactions (Gallagher et al, 1999).

Asparaginase II, interferes with the incorporation of amino acids into tumour protein in cell cultures (Mashburn & Wriston, 1964), it also inhibited the synthesis of protein under the direction of bacteriophage f2 RNA in cell-free extracts of *E. coli* (Schwartz, 1965). Asparaginase from *E. coli* is inactive against tumour growth and does not interfere with protein synthesis in microbial extracts (Schwartz et al, 1966).

Since several types of tumour cells require L-asparagine for protein synthesis, they are deprived of an essential growth factor in the presence of L-asparaginase (Savitri & Azmi, 2003). Cancer cells differentiate themselves from normal cells in diminished expression of L-asparagine (Swain et al, 1993; Manna et al, 1995). Hence, they are not capable of producing L-asparagine, and mainly depend on the L-asparagine from the circulating plasma pools (Swain et al, 1993). Effective depletion of L-asparagine results in death of leukaemic cells but so far, tumour inhibitory activity has been demonstrated only with asparaginases from *E. coli*, *Erwinia aroideae* and *Serratia marcescens* (Dhevagi & Poorani, 2005). The administration of such an enzyme protein for a long duration has been reported to cause anaphylactic shock (Capizzi et al, 1971). Therefore, new serologically different L-asparaginase from new microbial sources with a similar therapeutic effect is highly desirable (Davis & Mingioli, 1950).

Asparaginase would serve to feed asparagine on the environment directly into this pathway. Neither its substrate asparagine nor its products, aspartic acid and ammonia, appear to act specifically to induce the formation of asparaginase II (Cedar & Schwartz, 1968). The use of asparaginase II in the treatment of neoplastic disease makes it important that the

enzyme be produced in large quantities. Production of extracellular anti-leukaemic enzyme L-asparaginase from marine Actinomycetes was carried out using three different media, tryptone glucose yeast extract broth and tryptone fructose yeast extract broth (Basha et al, 2009). The content of asparaginase varies widely in different strains of *E. coli*, however, in all strains the enzyme is localized in the periplasmic region between the plasma membrane and cell envelope (Campbell et al, 1967).

Although L-asparaginase inhibits tumour cell growth, studies of this phenomenon have been limited, usually because sufficient quantities of the enzyme were not available. Sewage water is considered as a reservoir of Coliform organisms. Thus, sewage water of Peoples campus was used for isolation of *E. coli*. Present study revealed that the *E. coli* isolates of Peoples campus possess potentials for production of L-asparaginase enzyme. In the present study, 35 isolates were examined for enzyme production among which *E. coli* VRY-15 showed maximum extracellular production of the enzyme. The enzymes isolated from *E. coli* and *Erwinia carotovora* are now being used in the treatment of acute lymphoblastic leukaemia (Dhevagi & Poorani, 2006). Amena et al (2010) carried out production of extra-cellular L-asparaginase by *Streptomyces gulbargensis* using groundnut cake extracts and obtained optimum enzyme production at pH 8.5, 40°C and 200 rev/min with 1×10^8 spores/ml inoculum size. Narayana et al (2007) reported yeast extract (2%) as the best nitrogen source for L-asparaginase production by *S. albidoflavus*. Maximum L-asparaginase production using 0.1% (w/v) L-asparagine as the sole source of nitrogen has been observed in *Enterobacter cloacae* (Nawaz et al, 1998) and *Aeromonas* sp. (Pattnaik et al, 2000). L-asparaginase from *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* 50071 showed maximum activity at pH 9 when incubated at 37°C for 30 min (El-Bessoumy et al, 2004).

The results of the present study also suggest that isolated L-asparaginase may prove to be a promising agent and requires further investigation of its potential anti-leukaemic activity. Asparaginase also find application in food manufacturing companies as it is used to reduce asparagine present in food and thereby, reduce the risk of formation of acrylamide (Olempska-Beer, 2006). Acrylamide is formed as a reaction product between asparagine and reducing sugars when certain foods are baked or fried at temperatures exceeding 120°C (Luning et al, 2006).

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